

FROM TRANSITION TO TRIAGE?

SHIFTING BUDGET PRIORITIES IN THE EU AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE GREEN AND JUST TRANSITION 2025 AND BEYOND

POLICY BRIEF

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The European Green Deal was launched as a cornerstone of the EU's commitment to achieving climate neutrality, alongside the digital and industrial transformation. While its implementation has led to significant progress, its goal of embedding long-term sustainability at the heart of economic policy remains only partially fulfilled, with signs of growing divergence. Recent years have seen a notable shift in fiscal and political priorities driven by geopolitical conflicts such as the Russo-Ukrainian war, the COVID-19 pandemic, and growing economic tensions, including the US-China trade war. In response, the EU and its member states have prioritised strengthening Europe's resilience to stress, aiming at building an independent, prosperous, secure, and thriving society and economy—as reflected in the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) proposal for 2028–2034.

Although the EU continues to uphold its global climate commitments publicly, the MFF proposal raises concerns by appearing to dilute these promises, with questions about the robustness of monitoring mechanisms and the scope and objectives of future green investments. The outlook at the level of EU Member States appears even more concerning, as climate-related development aid is decreasing, climate policies are weakening, and political instability limits the approach to long-term challenges such as climate change and environmental protection.

Europe's long-term green and social transition objectives risk being eroded as defence, strategic autonomy, and competitiveness increasingly dominate fiscal priorities. **To preserve its commitment to climate neutrality, the EU would need to pursue not only greater policy coherence among its member states but also deeper integration of climate objectives into all dimensions of its policies.** Green investment and sustainable funding would have to be firmly embedded within industrial, security, and fiscal strategies under a coherent and transparent framework of budgetary governance. Failing to do so could lead to short-term geopolitical imperatives undermining Europe's long-term sustainability and climate commitments.

I. Introduction

This brief examines how shifting budgetary priorities across the EU and its Member States are reshaping the landscape for domestic investment in the green and just transition, ensuring that the transition towards a climate-neutral economy is taking place in a balanced way, leaving no one behind.

Since 2020, successive crises—from the COVID-19 pandemic to Russo-Ukrainian war on Ukraine—have prompted the rapid reallocation of public resources toward security, defence, and industrial competitiveness. While climate goals remain formally embedded in EU strategies, fiscal and political realities are driving difficult trade-offs. Green and social transition spending is increasingly vulnerable: delayed, diluted, or deprioritised.

The brief also tries to map the reallocation of national public budgets in selected EU Member States since 2020, evaluating the influence of defence and industrial policy spending and the repercussions on green and just transition measures. It also seeks to provide a forward-looking scenario analysis to inform strategic choices towards 2030.

These strategies emphasise greater flexibility in fiscal rules, enhanced budgetary coherence, and the alignment of industrial aid with climate and equity objectives. It highlights the growing tension between short-term political needs and the structural investment required for climate neutrality, social resilience, and sustainable growth. To understand how this shift unfolds in practice, it is necessary to examine how fiscal priorities have been reordered at the EU level, starting with the MFF.

Box 1. The methodology of the brief

To produce this policy brief, we have relied on a diverse set of documents published by the European Union institutions, its Member States, and reputable outside sources, such as research published by NGOs. EU sources often have a publication delay of approximately two years, which, coupled with current political instability, limits the ability to conduct a fully comprehensive analysis of recent trends.

To assess whether the EU is on track to fulfil its international commitments, we have examined not only the proposed MFF but also national budgets and official political statements. However, data comparison remains challenging in some cases due to shifting budget categories and inconsistent figures, which complicates the analysis.

II. The Reordering of EU Budgetary Priorities

i. Shift in MFF Priorities (2021–2027 and 2028–2034)

The European Green Deal was launched as a cornerstone of the EU’s commitment to climate neutrality, aiming at anchoring long-term sustainability at the heart of its economic policy. However, the past five years have challenged the EU’s dedication to carbon neutrality, economic transformation, and social cohesion as embedded within the European Green Deal.

While the EU remains committed to incorporating environmental sustainability into its core economic strategy, it has restructured its budgetary and political agenda. Public finances have been dramatically strained by consecutive emergencies, including the COVID-19 pandemic, Russo-Ukrainian war, price volatility, energy shortages, and escalating geopolitical tensions. EU-level spending has been increasingly redirected toward immediate imperatives: military rearmament, energy price subsidies, border management, and industrial competitiveness. While green and just transition goals remain embedded in EU legislation and planning frameworks, their effective implementation now hinges on whether domestic public finance can keep pace or will delay those commitments in favour of increasing short-term challenges.

To assess whether the EU will be able to remain on a green path despite the onslaught of new challenges, this analysis examines the MFF, which sets out the Union’s overall expenditure priorities and provides the anchor for its annual budgets. The MFF therefore forms the basis for evaluating the EU’s practical commitment to climate action amidst emerging pressures.

Under the current 2021–2027 Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF), two expenditure headings are projected to decrease significantly: “Natural Resources and Environment” and “Neighbourhood and the World”. This trend appears to contradict the overarching narrative of the budget which, as presented by the European Commission (EC) in 2020, is designed to underpin Europe’s green and digital transition. Nevertheless, this green dimension is embedded across several other expenditure headings that channel substantial environmental investments, particularly within “Cohesion, Resilience, and Values” and through the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) (Council Regulation 2020/2093). Furthermore, although expenditure under the “Natural Resources and Environment” heading is decreasing, it remained the second largest allocation throughout the planned period, receiving around 33.8% of the total budget.

Figure 1: Commitment appropriations MFF 2021-2028. Based on: Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093.

Box 2. Just Transition Fund

A key concept embedded in the current MFF is that of just transition, asserting the need to ensure a balanced socioeconomic transition. Under the current MFF, the Commission set up the Just Transition Fund, intended to mitigate the adverse effects of the climate transition by supporting the most affected territories and workers concerned.

Interestingly, and following the previously explained trend of simplification for the period after 2028, the European Commission’s MFF proposal indicates a shift from a standalone Just Transition Fund towards integrating just transition objectives into the broader “National and Regional Partnership Plans” chapter. The concept of just transition remains core to the EU’s climate and social policy agenda, but the mechanism itself is evolving towards a more integrated and flexible framework that aligns with the wider objectives of cohesion, social rights, competitiveness, and sustainable development ([European Commission](#)). Thus, the current Just Transition Fund will likely not continue in its present form post-2028. This reshaping risks diluting dedicated funding for just transition objectives or mislabelling resources, potentially blending them with policies that may have distinct aims and priorities.

The proposal for the MFF 2028–2034 foresees a reduction in the number of budgetary chapters from seven to four, merging environmental and social priorities under broader chapters such as “Competitiveness, Prosperity, and Security.” Presented as a simplification, this structural shift erases the dedicated environmental chapter while claiming to embed green spending across wider portfolios, resulting in greater flexibility. However, although this could be seen as the much-desired integration of sustainability into a broader policy framework, it may jeopardize transparency and weaken oversight of climate-related investments ([European Commission](#)).

Quantitatively, the proposed MFF allocates approximately 35% of EU spending to climate and environmental objectives. Nevertheless, the Commission’s proposal relies on ex-ante accounting methods rather than verified results. Programmes are assigned a “climate relevance coefficient,” which runs the risk of inflating the share of green spending without measuring actual outcomes. The European Court of Auditors has repeatedly warned that such aggregation produces unreliable indicators (see Box 3). **As a result, the 35% figure represents a political signal and statement of intent rather than a verified investment target.**

Figure 2. EU Budgetary Chapters MFF 2021-2027 vs MFF 2028-2034. Based on: European Commission, “A dynamic EU Budget for the priorities of the future - The MFF 2028-2034”, and Council Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2020/2093.

Box 3. Challenges in monitoring green spendings in the EU

Furthermore, the attempt to integrate environmental objectives into the agenda of industrial competitiveness, in the absence of robust accounting mechanisms, may lead to broad but often superficial claims of environmental alignment, exposing the EU to a growing “greenwashing” phenomenon. Several examples highlight the difficulties of integrating green objectives across different areas.

The European Court of Auditors criticised the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023–2027 Strategic Plan Regulation (CAP SPs) for not aligning with the EU’s climate and environmental ambitions. Similarly, programmes like the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) exhibit several issues. According to the Court of Auditors, the European Commission cannot reliably evaluate the performance of measures contributing to the green transition due to significant limitations in the monitoring framework.

The Commission’s reporting is limited to climate-related amounts allocated ex ante, which do not correspond to the actual costs of implemented measures. Consequently, achieved milestones and targets do not consistently reflect genuine progress or ambition toward the green transition. This makes reported figures on green spending unreliable indicators of actual expenditure.

Focusing now on the qualitative implications, the only subchapter from the MFF proposal for 2028–2034 that can be directly linked to supporting EU green commitments is the actions under the heading “Clean Transition and Industrial Decarbonisation,” found within the European Competitiveness Fund. Notably, while most funding windows within the Fund show progressive growth, the “Clean Transition and Industrial Decarbonisation” allocation remains relatively low until 2031, when it suddenly increases by EUR 10 billion, or 2.6%, in a single year (see Figure 3).

This window accounts for about 3.8% of the overall EU budget for 2028–2034. It raises questions about the rationale behind this atypical allocation and whether it signals a short-term shift away from green funding, with a possible refocus on climate finance after 2030. A decrease in transparency, coupled with a widespread dilution of green expenditure, leads to questioning how the previous “Natural Resources and Environment” chapter, representing around 33.8% of the 2021–2027 budget, has been absorbed and its relevance maintained under the new structure.

Figure 3. European Competitiveness Fund: Proposed Budget Allocation under the MFF 2028–2034 (EUR million). Based on: European Commission, “A dynamic EU Budget for the priorities of the future - The MFF 2028-2034,” COM/2025/570, Brussels, 16 July 2025.

The inclusion of “Clean Transition and Decarbonisation” within a broader competitiveness framework reflects the EU’s effort to balance industrial and climate goals. However, this balance appears uneven. The European Competitiveness Fund, which aims to strengthen Europe’s technological and industrial sovereignty, prioritizes innovation and productivity over measurable environmental impact. Its placement within a broad competitiveness heading raises concerns about the true green objectives of this allocation. The European Competitiveness Fund, working in synergy with Horizon Europe, is intended to provide seamless support to European innovators and help the Union build a competitive edge in strategic sectors. **This may either lead to a wider inclusion of transition objectives within the EU industrial strategy or to a prioritisation of economic growth over effective and beneficial environmental investment.**

The Commission explicitly reaffirms its commitment to the former path, aiming for an integrated climate and industrial policy. It reasserts its commitment to long-term CO2 neutrality goals and its values through the maintenance of the “do no significant harm” and the “climate resilience by design” principles. This should ensure that EU-funded activities do not cause significant harm to climate and environmental objectives while preparing for and better managing climate risks. However, in the proposed MFF 2028-2034, these safeguards may be described as procedural in nature rather than strategic. Through central databases or procedural harmonisation, these measures may strengthen monitoring, enforcement, and compliance mechanisms. However, they do not necessarily foster deeper ambition or innovation. **The risk is that meeting requirements becomes a box-ticking exercise rather than an instrument for genuine and practical implementation** ([European Commission](#)).

Box 4. “Do no significant harm” and “climate resilience by design” principles

The “do no significant harm” and the “climate resilience by design” principles are guiding approaches towards Europe’s clean transition, applied throughout European climate funding and investment policy.

The “do no significant harm” principle is defined through the EU Taxonomy Regulation and included in the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) and other funds. Through an assessment for potential harm to six objectives, this principle ensures that EU-funded activities are not detrimental to climate and environmental goals. If one of those objectives is damaged by a specific project, it breaks the principle ([Regulation 2020/852](#)).

The “climate resilience by design” principle has emerged from global project development, pushing organisations to integrate resilience measures within design and planning schemes. It aims at the integration of climate adaptation into project objectives, reporting, and technical standards, promoting investments or activities that are intrinsically resistant or adaptable to adverse climate impacts.

ii. Security and Competitiveness: New Budget Giants

To assess whether the EU is genuinely advancing a green and just transition, it is essential to examine current EU public discourse and policy objectives. The Commission's Communication "A Dynamic EU Budget for the Priorities of the Future" identifies three overarching priorities for the Union: defence, competitiveness, and flexibility. These themes dominate the proposed MFF for 2028–2034, whose largest funding headings channel resources primarily toward security and industrial competitiveness.

Competitiveness and industrial sovereignty have emerged as defining policy priorities. Through initiatives such as the EU Industrial Plan, the Net-Zero Industry Act, and the relaxation of state aid rules, EU Member States are prompted to direct substantial public funds toward strategic sectors like batteries, semiconductors, and hydrogen. However, many of these investments lack robust environmental or social conditionality criteria. **In the absence of clear safeguards, industrial subsidies risk reinforcing existing inequalities or supporting high-carbon technologies under the guise of transition.**

The growing emphasis on defence and industrial competitiveness, when not systematically linked to climate objectives, threatens to crowd out the fiscal and political space required for a genuine green and just transition.

Despite this general shift, some voices within the European Union continue to advocate for a stronger climate orientation in EU budgetary and policy frameworks. Under the banner "A Strong Europe in a Changing World," the Danish Presidency has articulated two overarching goals: a secure Europe and a competitive, green Europe.

These priorities are embedded across its sectoral agenda, which seeks to bolster Europe's resilience amid geopolitical uncertainty while maintaining momentum on sustainable economic growth and the green transition. The Presidency also underscores the need to align industrial competitiveness with environmental ambition, positioning green investment as a source of long-term strategic strength.

This ambition was partially reflected in the Council's agreement on 5 Nov 2025 on a –90% net GHG cut by 2040—a headline target matching the Commission's proposal—but with certain elements weakening the ambition: An allowance for up to 5% of 1990-level emissions to be met via international credits, a one-year Emission Trading System 2 (ETS2) delay to 2028, and a clearer role for engineered removals. Compared with the Commission's tighter architecture (notably a 3% credit cap and no ETS2 delay), the Council deal effectively lowers domestic effort to roughly –85% by 2040. This places it below independent advice from the European Scientific Advisory Board (and PIK-linked research) calling for –90% to –95% domestic by 2040, and behind IPCC-consistent 2035 markers—illustrating the Presidency's pragmatic consensus-building, but also the remaining ambition gap to a 1.5°C-aligned pathway.

THIS IS NEITHER TRIUMPH NOR TRICK—IT KEEPS THE EU’S BANNER UP BUT TRIMS THE SAIL.

The –90% by 2040 headline sustains the EU’s leadership narrative and gives the Danish Presidency a tangible deliverable, yet the added flexibilities (higher offset use, an ETS2 delay, greater reliance on engineered removals) lower domestic effort and push risk into the 2030s, widening the gap to science-based pathways. **This deal preserves the EU’s role as a climate pace-setter on paper, but its expanded flexibilities test credibility—keeping ambition alive, not fully honest.**

This approach contrasts with the broader narrative emerging from the Trio Programme of Poland, Denmark, and Cyprus, which is organised around three main themes: “A Strong and Secure Europe,” “A Prosperous and Competitive Europe,” and “A Free and Democratic Europe.”

While the twin transition (digital and green) appears under the competitiveness theme, it is not treated as an independent or cross-cutting objective, reflecting a more cautious framing of climate priorities ([General Secretariat of the Council](#)).

Early signals from the subsequent Trio Presidency, which will include Ireland (July–December 2026), suggest a further deprioritisation of climate concerns. In his speech on 6 May 2025, Thomas Byrne, Ireland’s Minister of State for European Affairs and Defence, outlined six priorities: geopolitical challenges, communicating Europe, enlargement, the EU budget, competitiveness, and security and defence ([Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade](#)). Green commitments were notably absent. **While such statements are not legally binding, they nonetheless indicate that the Danish effort to integrate green and industrial strategies may not be sustained by future presidencies, raising concerns about the continuity and depth of the EU’s commitment to the green and just transition.**

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To sum up, although green commitments remain formally embedded within the European policy agenda and are increasingly mainstreamed across different sectors, it is not clear whether their implementation will be true to the initial expectations. Green and industrial spending still compete rather than complement one another in the budgetary sphere. Meanwhile, safeguards, such as the 35% climate and environment allocation, are often methodologically weak or raise questions about transparency and effectiveness.

Overall, EU policy development lacks a coherent, systemic momentum and is further undermined by limited coordination among Member States, leaving the green and just transition vulnerable to fragmentation and uneven progress. In the following section, we will seek to distinguish overarching European trends in the transition from the insights drawn from current budgetary data, political commitments, and policy reports.

Figure 4. EU Member States Military Spending (constant prices in USD millions, 2023). Based on: SIPRI Database.

MFF Proposal Changes

New Budgetary Giants

Key findings:

- The MFF 2028–2034 shifts from a dedicated environmental budget to a dispersed integration model, which risks masking stagnation in real and implemented green investment.
- The MFF’s integration of green goals into competitiveness strategies risks subordinating environmental objectives to industrial ones, converting the Green Deal from a transformative agenda into an auxiliary growth tool.
- Competitiveness and industrial sovereignty have emerged as defining policy priorities. Despite this shift, some voices within the Union continue to advocate for a stronger climate orientation in EU budgetary and policy frameworks, struggling to align industrial competitiveness with environmental ambition.
- This policy reconciliation is reflected both in the EU’s broad “Clean Transition and Decarbonisation” plan and in the horizontal target of allocating 35% of EU budget spending to climate and environmentally related objectives. However, this approach faces several challenges, including greenwashing, a lack of robust monitoring mechanisms, and policy fragmentation.

III. Budgetary Reprioritisation in EU Member States: Green and Just Transition Commitment under Pressure

i. EU Member States' Climate Commitments

As budgetary priorities have shifted, the available fiscal space for ambitious and sustained investment in the green and just transition has narrowed. Climate-related spending has been particularly constrained, with energy efficiency programs, renewable energy deployment, and climate adaptation funding often delayed, reduced, or reallocated. In several Member States, planned investments have been rebranded as “green” without meaningful changes in content or impact, raising concerns about methodological consistency and potential greenwashing.

Social investment, essential for ensuring a fair and inclusive transition, has also suffered. **Support for vulnerable groups such as low-income households, fossil fuel-dependent workers, and regions undergoing structural transformation remains insufficient and often fragmented.** Furthermore, reskilling programmes, green job initiatives, and territorial cohesion measures funded under the Just Transition Mechanism (see Box 4) and national co-financing schemes often fall short of addressing the scale of social and economic disruption expected.

Industrial transition efforts show mixed results. While some Member States actively promote clean technology sectors, these measures or funding are not always linked to climate or social criteria. As a result, the **coherence between industrial, social, and climate policies remains partial and uneven across the EU.**

In parallel, geopolitical tensions and the increasing sentiment of insecurity in Europe, driven by the Russo-Ukrainian war and the discussion on the reliability of commitments to NATO, have led to a rapid expansion of defence and security budgets across Europe. Germany's EUR 100 billion special defence fund is one of the most prominent examples, but similar patterns are visible elsewhere. **Military modernisation, cyberdefence, and border infrastructure now account for growing shares of national budgets.**

This reorientation has tangible implications for climate action. The annual Climate Change Performance Index (CCPI), an independent monitoring tool assessing the climate mitigation performance worldwide, unveils stagnation or even decline in European climate efforts. Except for certain cases – such as Romania, Poland, Ireland, or Spain – the **overall situation has not improved in recent years** ([Germanwatch](#)).

Figure 5. Climate Policy Performance Index in European Countries 2022 vs 2025. Adapted from: Germanwatch, NewClimate Institute, and Climate Action Network (2022 and 2025).

Figure 6. Climate Policy Performance Index in European Countries 2022 vs 2025. Adapted from: Germanwatch, NewClimate Institute, and Climate Action Network (2022 and 2025).

Within the CCPI, there is a subindicator labelled “Climate Policy” that assesses not only national emissions policies and targets but also sectoral policies, targets, and their implementation.

As the colour-coded results illustrate, the number of countries demonstrating high performance in Climate Policy sharply declined from 10 to just 1 in 2025. Current climate targets and their implementation show no discernible improvement and remain insufficient to limit global warming to 1.5°C.

ii. EU Member States' Climate International Finance

In the following section, we will build on the results from our previous policy brief: "[Budgetary Trends in the European Union and its Member States and Implications for Climate Finance.](#)" The document delves into the stagnation of international climate finance, a significant global trend with profound impacts on green and just transition investments.

Official Development Assistance (ODA) has historically been the main source of financing for development aid since its conceptual consolidation by the OECD's Development Assistance Committee (DAC) in 1969. Its emergence sought to bring consistency and clarity to growing flows of development assistance.

This assistance has grown crucial for climate finance, as over 30% is normally allocated to climate-related projects, and this share has been progressively increasing. **However, mirroring worldwide climate trends, ODA has recently declined, with key donors such as Germany and Sweden reducing their total contributions.** Germany's net ODA disbursements dropped 23%, from USD 41,250 million in 2022 to USD 31,860 million in 2024. While still above the average, Sweden's total contribution reached its lowest share in the past 14 years, with its share of GNI falling to 0.79% ([OECD, Data Explorer](#)). This tendency clearly reflects a deprioritisation of climate finance and development aid in general, aligning with previously observed trends at the European level.

Figure 7: ODA Net Disbursement per Country (USD millions).
Source: [OECD, Data Explorer](#).

iii. EU Member States' budgets in Practice: Current Trends

From 2020 to 2025, EU Member States have experienced a marked shift in domestic public spending priorities. Initially, the post-pandemic recovery packages—including the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF)—placed strong emphasis on green investments. While its accounting was not completely reliable, the requirement for 37% of national Recovery and Resilience Plans (RRPs) to support climate objectives reflected a shared ambition for a green recovery.

However, this momentum began to shift in 2022. The outbreak of the Russo-Ukrainian war led to European governments redirecting funds toward defence, military infrastructure, and energy security. Several EU Member States introduced large-scale subsidies to shield consumers from rising energy prices—often supporting fossil-fuel-based systems. Simultaneously, new pressures emerged from inflation, social unrest, and increasing demands for competitiveness support in strategic sectors.

By 2024, the reintroduction of the EU's fiscal rules further tightened the budgetary space for discretionary investment.

MANY GOVERNMENTS HAVE RESPONDED BY SCALING BACK OR DELAYING GREEN PROGRAMMES. OTHERS HAVE RESORTED TO RE-LABELLING EXISTING SPENDING AS "GREEN" WITHOUT ENSURING ADDITIONALITY.

The framework is intended to promote sustainability and support the green, digital, and resilient transformation of EU economies. Yet, in practice, the revised fiscal rules make it harder to finance new green investments, especially for countries with high debt and deficits. This means deficit-financed green investments can be limited from the very start of fiscal adjustment periods, with no significant exceptions ([European Commission](#)).

While countries can request longer adjustment timelines to ease budgetary pressure, green investments often fail to meet the criteria for growth-enhancing expenditure, weakening incentives for additional public spending on decarbonisation. **Unless the framework evolves to better reflect the investment needs of the green transition there is a real risk that climate goals could be slowed rather than supported.**

In parallel, large allocations were made to defence (e.g., Germany's EUR 100 billion special fund) and industrial subsidies (e.g., to semiconductor or battery industries), often without clear climate or social safeguards. The cumulative effect is a gradual **crowding out of long-term transition investment in favour of short-term stabilisation and security agendas.**

It may be argued that once short-term political concerns are addressed or fade, these objectives will be deprioritised and return to a secondary status. This intention is reflected in the EU's planned increase in funding for "Clean Transition and Industrial Decarbonisation" beginning in 2031, alongside Sweden's projected reduction in defence spending after 2028. However, this later commitment appears to conflict with more recent Swedish strategic plans to meet NATO's 3.5% defence spending target by 2030.

Illustrating the budgetary change, several European countries have been selected, and their available published data analysed next. This data concerns budgetary intentions and prospects, aiming to outline the anticipated course of the green and just transition.

iv. Case Profiles

Sweden

As previously noted, Sweden plans to exponentially increase its defence and contingency spending, reaching SEK 234 billion by 2027 and making it the country’s largest public expenditure, accounting for

26.2% of the total budget. Justice spending is also projected to rise significantly, from SEK 78 billion in 2024 to SEK 108 billion in 2028. In parallel, industrial and competitiveness-related sectors—mainly transport and communication, and to a lesser degree, energy and economic and financial administration—are projected to expand steadily over the same period.

Conversely, healthcare and social services are forecast to decline slightly, dropping to SEK 118 billion by 2028, while education and academic research show moderate growth, from SEK 98 billion in 2024 to SEK 107 billion by 2028. The budget for climate, environment, and nature initially rises to SEK 20 billion in 2026 but then falls back to SEK 17 billion by 2028, signalling limited long-term prioritisation.

Overall, the budget reveals a clear reorientation of government priorities toward defence, justice, and infrastructure, while allocations for social welfare, environmental protection, and agricultural development remain static or decline. These shifts mirror a broader fiscal and political trend in Sweden, emphasising national security, industrial competitiveness, and fiscal discipline, often at the expense of climate and social investment.

Figure 6: EU Bilateral Aid Climate Finance to Developing Countries 2021-2024 (provided amount in EUR millions). Source: Support to developing countries - Reporting year 2021, Reporting year 2022, Reporting year 2023, Reporting year 2024, Reporting year 2025.

Key findings:

- Sweden plans to significantly increase defence spending, reaching SEK 234 billion by 2027, becoming the largest public expenditure.
- The Ministry of Justice and the Ministry of Transport and Communication also show strong growth, with the former rising from SEK 78 billion in 2024 to SEK 108 billion in 2028, and the latter growing from SEK 81 billion to SEK 121 billion.
- Healthcare and social services are projected to decline slightly by 2028, while education and academic research are projected to experience moderate growth.
- Climate, environment, and nature budgets peak in 2026 but decline by 2028, reflecting a cautious approach amid rising defence and justice expenditures.

If we examine Germany's budgetary trends following the presentation of the 2026 draft budget, several key patterns emerge. Firstly, **although the total budget responds to rising inflation with an overall increase of 3.57%, the additional funds are not distributed evenly to offset inflationary pressures.** Instead, they are primarily concentrated within the Ministry of Defence and the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs.

Germany

Overall, ministerial allocations remain largely stable, with no significant structural changes compared to previous years. **Among the few ministries experiencing growth, the increase in defence spending is particularly notable.** The substantial rise introduced in 2025 will not only be sustained but further reinforced in 2026. This development firmly establishes the Ministry of Defence as the second most funded ministry, following the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs. Following the stagnation tendency, **the 2026 draft maintains the funding cuts introduced in 2025 for the Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ),** the principal institution responsible for Germany's external climate finance and international development cooperation.

At first glance (Figure 10), **the Special Fund for Infrastructure and Climate Neutrality (SVIK in German), with planned investments of EUR 500 billion over twelve years, might appear to signal a renewed commitment to Germany's environmental objectives.** However, a closer look at the fund reveals that the fund's primary purpose is to stimulate economic growth, foster employment, and enhance business competitiveness. **In practice, only about a quarter of its resources are directed toward achieving climate neutrality by 2045.** Despite its title, climate-related measures play a secondary role, as most investments are channelled into transport infrastructure and digitalisation. These priorities closely mirror the broader objectives of the MFF 2028–2034 proposal, seeking to make Europe –and Germany in particular–economically stronger and more competitive.

A few concerns have emerged that this investment strategy may reinforce climate-damaging policies.

Figure 9. German Federal Budget 2022-2026 per Ministry (in EUR million).
 Based on: Bundesministerium der Finanzen, Digital Federal Budget.
 *The 2026 data represent figures from the government’s draft budget for that year.

Among the most contentious leading clues is the **CSU’s electoral pledge to fully reinstate diesel subsidies for agriculture from 2026**, reversing previous phase-out efforts. This move has been widely criticised by environmental economists for perpetuating fossil fuel dependency and inefficient agricultural practices. Moreover, the government’s decision to delay its 2030 coal exit target further undermines its climate commitments and casts doubt on Germany’s capacity to deliver a rapid and credible energy transition

Taken together, these trends suggest a clear shift toward prioritising economic and political pragmatism over environmental ambition. **While the emphasis on competitiveness and infrastructure may strengthen short-term economic resilience, it risks eroding Germany’s long-standing role as a leader in EU climate policy and weakening collective progress toward the Green Deal objectives.**

Figure 10. Intended federal expenditure from the SVIK by area.
 Source: Federal Ministry of Finance (Germany), "Schwerpunktthema: In die Zukunft investieren".

Key findings:

- The 2026 draft budget maintains the increased defence spending from 2025, positioning Defence as the second largest ministry. Simultaneously, it consolidates the cuts on the BMZ Ministry, directly affecting international climate finance.
- The Special Fund for Infrastructure and Climate Neutrality (SVIK) plans EUR 500 billion in investments over twelve years, but only a quarter of this targets climate neutrality; the majority goes to transport and digitalisation..
- Concerns exist over climate policy setbacks, including the reinstatement of agricultural diesel subsidies and the retreat from the 2030 coal exit target, jeopardising Germany's climate leadership.

France

While France currently faces a politically complex and turbulent environment, it nonetheless illustrates how **geopolitical developments, accompanied by increasing debt, have deeply influenced budgetary trajectories. Following the European tendency, defence and security have taken a central role in the budgetary agenda.** The budget allocated to the Ministry of Armed Forces surged by 36.6% in a single year, from almost EUR 70 billion to over EUR 95 billion in 2025. Increased defence spending is expected to bolster France's domestic industrial and technological competitiveness, particularly in sectors related to defence and aerospace. **When looking at certain budgetary missions such as "Durable Ecology, Development, and Mobility," we observe a reduction of 26% since 2023, from EUR 35.7 billion to EUR 26.3 billion.**

Despite some overlapping elements among these budgetary missions, analysing consistent functional groupings reveals salient spending patterns. When grouped into general categories such as "Green," "Defence," "Social," "Economic and Industrial," and "Aid for Developing Countries" spending, clear tendencies emerge. While distinct, **all groups show a general increase in spending except for the "Green" category, which experiences a sharp decline.** However, the increase in social spending remains limited compared to the other categories, which may indicate that the depreciation in climate-related budgets is accompanied by diminished social funding.

President Macron's positioning echoes broader debates within the EU about balancing ambitious climate goals with the need to maintain a level playing field against global competitors like the United States and China. He arguably presents these aims as opposing objectives, depicting the EU's Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and related green regulations as a potential threat to the competitiveness of Europe's fragile economy. He remarked that **"we ourselves have supported certain regulations with very good intentions, but, given the challenges we face today, we must have the flexibility to suspend intentions until we have regained our ability to compete."** This aligns with recent shifts in France's budgetary priorities and partially resonates with the MFF's renewed emphasis on enhancing economic competitiveness. Notably, President Macron's call goes beyond a mere regulatory pause and has extended to advocating the indefinite postponement or even elimination of aspects of the CSRD and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD), drawing criticism from environmental advocates who warn that this could undermine Europe's climate leadership.

Figure 11. French Budgetary Expenditure per category 2023-2026 (EUR billions).

Based on: Budget de l'État.

*The 2026 data derives from the initial Draft Budget Law (PLF in French), whereas data for previous years come from the adopted budget or Initial Finance Law (LFI in French).

Figure 12. Budgetary Variation 2023-2026 in France (in %).

Based on: Budget de l'État.

*To create this image, categories were combined. For a detailed breakdown, please refer to Figure 11 above.

Key findings:

- France’s defence spending is accelerating, aiming to double by 2027 with a projected budget of EUR 64 billion, driven by geopolitical pressures and security imperatives.
- When grouped into general categories, “Green Spending” stands out as the only one that does not increase. On the contrary, it sharply decreases from 2023 to 2026.
- France’s President, Emmanuel Macron, criticises EU green regulations (CSRD) as a threat to competitiveness and supports suspending aspects to regain economic strength.

Spain

While the consequences of climate change are visible worldwide, certain countries have been disproportionately affected over the past three decades. While the consequences of climate change are visible worldwide, certain countries have been disproportionately affected over the past three decades. **The Germanwatch Climate Risk Index describes Europe as the fastest-warming continent and includes Spain, Italy, and Greece among the top ten most impacted countries between 1993 and 2022.** This standing is largely due to both the high absolute and relative number of fatalities. In Mediterranean countries, these deaths were primarily caused by extreme heatwaves, floods, and wildfires. Notably, Spain has experienced approximately 27,000 fatalities over the last thirty years, along with around USD 25 billion in economic losses ([Germanwatch](#)).

Considering the impacts of climate change, corresponding policy responses and budgetary measures are to be expected. **Spain has recently restated its international climate commitments through the announcement of the “Spanish Strategy for International Climate Financing”** ([Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico](#)). This strategy plans to mobilise EUR 1,350 million by 2025 and aims to double Spain’s multilateral and bilateral ODA, with a particular focus on adaptation projects. Domestically, recent initiatives include the Climate Emergency Plan (Royal Decree 214/2025), which imposes mandatory carbon reporting and reduction obligations on large companies and public bodies, and the updated National Integrated Energy and Climate Plan, which sets ambitious targets for greenhouse gas emissions reduction and renewable energy expansion. However, these commitments largely remain theoretical. Both ODA contributions and the state budget have shown limited changes. The 2023 General Budget has been extended twice, reflecting the political instability the country faces. Furthermore, the government missed the deadline to present the 2026 State Budget. Although officials insist it will be submitted by year’s end, the coalition relies on regional parties that have already threatened to withdraw support. Consequently, the implementation of these climate and energy measures risks being delayed or even abandoned if political instability persists or early elections are called.

Amid escalating security threats, Spain is also significantly increasing its defence spending. The government has announced a EUR 10.5 billion plan to raise defence expenditure from 1.3 to 2% of GDP, still below NATO’s 5% target. Interestingly, a portion of this increased spending is allocated to climate-related security measures. **Approximately EUR 1.75 billion, 17% of the defence budget, is earmarked for disaster relief and climate resilience initiatives, reflecting the view that “climate change kills” and framing climate action as an integral aspect of national security.** As the EU continues to navigate complex industrial and defence policy challenges, Spain’s experience offers valuable insights into the potential for aligning environmental sustainability with both national and collective security objectives. Furthermore, it illustrates the political complications and obstacles that climate-related measures are facing across Europe.

Key findings:

- Spain ranks among the world’s ten most climate-affected countries, with 27000 deaths and USD 25 billion in losses since 1993.
- Despite new plans like the Climate Emergency Plan and the EUR 1350 million climate finance strategy, political instability delays real implementation.
- Defence spending is rising to 2% of GDP, with 17% directed to climate resilience and disaster relief, framing climate action as an integral aspect of national security.

Denmark

As mentioned earlier, **under the slogan “A Strong Europe in a Changing World,” the Danish Presidency has aimed to reinforce Europe’s resilience amid geopolitical uncertainty and strategic competition.**

It seeks not only to build a secure and competitive Europe but also a green one, including climate action as a key area on the agenda. It is reasonable to assume that these priorities will be mirrored by the Danish government and legislative bodies. Denmark has reaffirmed its commitment to international climate finance, pledging around USD 500 million annually in grant-based climate support to developing countries. In line with similar initiatives in Spain, the Danish Ministry of Defence has introduced a **Green Action Plan for 2021–2025**, focusing on reducing the environmental impact of military operations and promoting sustainable practices within the defence sector. Notably, **a portion of Denmark’s defence budget is earmarked for climate-related security measures**: approximately USD 4.26 billion is allocated to enhance Arctic defence capabilities, which includes addressing climate-induced challenges in the region. **This integration of climate considerations within security budgets takes place in a context of significant increases in national defence spending**, which now exceeds 3% of GDP. These investments not only attempt to strengthen national security but also support domestic industrial and technological competitiveness.

The energy sector remains the backbone of Denmark’s green competitiveness agenda. Denmark is one of the EU’s frontrunners in offshore wind electricity and has introduced the concept of “energy islands,” notably in the North Sea or Bornholm, designed to decentralise offshore wind electricity production and distribution. However, several flagship projects have faced repeated delays due to escalating costs, permitting bottlenecks, and disputes over financing models. While the long-term ambition remains intact, the pace of implementation has slowed down, creating a widening gap between political ambition and delivery capacity.

While progress on green policies faces challenges, defence spending enjoys broad political support due to the immediacy of security imperatives. Implementation of initiatives like the Green Action Plan or broader renewable energy projects has been slowed by political debates, budgetary constraints, and administrative delays. Furthermore, energy infrastructure, though strategically critical, lacks the same urgency framing, leaving major renewable projects vulnerable to delay despite their centrality to both climate goals and energy sovereignty. Consequently, while defence and defence-related industrial investments rapidly rise in response to external pressures – energy, climate, and green policies – despite strong commitments, they risk stagnation due to slower implementation and political complications.

Key findings:

- Denmark has solid climate-related commitments supported by robust financial and policy measures. Notably, it pledges at least USD 500 million annually in climate finance to developing countries. Additionally, its Green Action Plan 2021–2025 aims to reduce the environmental impact of military operations and promote sustainable defence practices.
- While overall defence spending exceeds 3% of GDP, supporting both national security and industrial competitiveness, EUR 4.26 billion of the defence budget is allocated to climate-related security measures, especially in the Arctic.
- Despite strong commitments, green policy implementation faces delays due to political debates, budgetary constraints, and administrative complications, creating a contrast where defence and industrial investments rise rapidly while climate initiatives risk further stagnation.

*Climate Change
Performance Index*

*Official Development
Assistance*

Fiscal Tightening

*Political
Fragmentation*

Key findings:

- The annual Climate Change Performance Index, an independent tool assessing the climate mitigation performance worldwide, shows stagnation or decline in European climate efforts.
- Official Development Assistance, a crucial element of climate finance, has steadily decreased and is expected to decline further.
- Amid fiscal tightening, climate and development spending are stagnating, while defence and security budgets are rising significantly.
- Green and climate-friendly policies remain under implementation but face strong political obstacles and persistent delays.
- National approaches are fragmented, both between states and across fiscal allocations for climate, defence, and industrial sectors. As a consequence of the former, long-term green initiatives must compete for funding against urgent short-term security concerns.

IV. Risks, Scenarios, and Opportunities for the Future

As highlighted in previous sections, fiscal paradigms are shifting, with defence and industrial priorities outpacing climate initiatives. It remains uncertain whether EU priorities will realign in the medium term to fully embrace the principles enshrined in the European Green Deal or whether climate and sustainability goals will take a back seat in the face of geopolitical and competitiveness pressures. Looking ahead, the trajectory of green and just transition investments in the EU depends on a complex interplay of political, economic, and regulatory forces.

Meanwhile, the revised economic governance framework—set to apply from 2024—will condition national fiscal choices for the foreseeable future ([European Commission](#)). Rising debt service costs, volatile energy markets, and ongoing geopolitical instability may continue to favour short-term and security-oriented spending. While fiscal rules that limit government deficits help curb excessive public debt, they can negatively affect investment in long-term public goods, such as climate protection. At the same time, growing climate impacts and social inequalities could re-energise the political mandate for a more ambitious and equitable transition. New resources (e.g., Emission Trading System revenues, Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism proceeds) and the application of “green golden rules” under fiscal governance reform could help create protected space for long-term investment if deployed coherently. These so-called “green golden rules” refer to a fiscal mechanism that links permissible government deficits to emission reductions or carbon pricing, thereby introducing a framework for fiscal responsibility that supports climate objectives.

Below, we present three broad scenarios that the EU may follow, depending on the practical policy responses chosen:

Baseline Risk Scenario

Green and social spending is stagnating or declining as fiscal space shrinks and political momentum fades. The long-term focus has shifted toward security and competitiveness, relegating the green transition to a secondary priority. This shift perpetuates the current fragmented approach, with defence and, notably, industrial incentives managed separately by Member States. Competitiveness policies are pursued with limited integration of climate objectives, and are expected to reflect diverging goals rather than a coherent strategy.

Fragmented Investment Scenario

Climate, industrial, and social priorities advance in parallel but without strategic coherence or synergies. While green funding is not being reduced, it competes for fiscal resources with industrial investments. Political support for the Green Deal varies significantly but has generally increased in certain areas, such as renewable energy, and it has been partially integrated into the technology sector. Coordination between these policy areas remains limited; however, a partial alignment exists, resulting in moderate policy coherence.

Resilient Transition Scenario

Fiscal and policy frameworks are aligned to protect and expand investment in climate neutrality, equity, and sustainability. This represents an idealistic scenario that, while likely unachievable in the short term, could serve as a guiding model towards an optimal future situation. It envisions the implementation of the previously mentioned green golden rule, supported by broad public and political consensus. For its attainment, strategic climate investments combined with equity measures would be integrated into comprehensive fiscal and industrial strategies across the EU and its Member States. This scenario depicts the emergence of green industrial growth, simultaneously accompanied by robust social and climate policies designed to ensure a fair and just transition for all.

The outcome will largely depend on whether EU Member States and institutions will be ready to make the effort to align fiscal, industrial, and climate policies decisively under a coherent strategic vision for the transition decade ahead.

The EU claims to be committed to embedding green spending deeply into its agenda, pledging to allocate 35% of the total budget to environmental and climate-related initiatives. However, **the precise scope and impact of these investments remain uncertain, with persistent concerns about greenwashing and fragmented monitoring systems.** Still, the effort to integrate industrial policy into the green transition could accelerate the development of green-oriented sectors such as renewable energy, clean technologies, and sustainable infrastructure.

Moreover, new initiatives to assess the climate implications of defence spending, along with a growing understanding of security budgets as encompassing climate-related risks, as illustrated by Spain's case, may lead to a climate-conscious reinterpretation of defence investments. Yet, while the EU's continued commitment to the Green Deal and international climate goals could sustain momentum, full implementation remains unlikely without stronger coordination and political will across Member States, both of which are currently uneven and, in some cases, receding.

Amid a political shift toward governments less focused on environmental priorities, policy alignment appears increasingly remote. Defence and competitiveness agendas are gaining ground, supported by EU financial mechanisms and national priorities. By contrast, **climate action and development aid –despite overall budgetary expansion– are stagnating or declining.** While some aspects of the green transition will continue to receive funding, limited fiscal space and competing priorities raise questions about the effectiveness and credibility of these efforts.

Current EU policy trajectories most closely resemble a *Fragmented Investment Scenario*: some progress continues in climate and industrial domains, but without strategic coherence or a designed and monitored pathway. National governments are prioritising defence and economic resilience, often at the expense of transition spending. **As fiscal constraints tighten, green investment risks stagnation, dilution, or relabelling, moving EU Member States closer to a *Baseline Risk Scenario* where climate ambition weakens rather than deepens.**

Dimension	Baseline Risk Scenario	Fragmented Investment Scenario	Resilient Transition Scenario
Fiscal environment	Tight fiscal rules limit green/social investment; no green-golden rules	Mixed use of flexibility; green and industrial spending coexist but compete	Green golden rules applied; new own resources expand fiscal space
Political momentum	Post-2024 shift toward security and competitiveness; transition deprioritised	Green Deal partially implemented; political support varies by country	Broad public and political support for the transition renewed post-2024
Climate spending	Declines or stagnates; re-labelling replaces real investment	Advances in some areas (e.g., renewables), but lacks a systemic push	Expanded, strategic climate investment integrated across sectors
Social investment	Reduced support for vulnerable groups and regions	Targeted support via short-term schemes; structural neglect persists	Strong focus on equity, inclusion, and social buffers
Industrial policy	Focus on sovereignty and reindustrialisation without climate links	Green tech supported, but with weak social/territorial safeguards	Industrial strategy aligned with green and just transition goals
Policy coherence	Low: Fragmented planning, conflicting objectives	Moderate: Partial alignment across domains, limited coordination	High: Integrated fiscal, climate, and industrial strategy across Member States

Figure 13. Scenario Matrix: Budgetary Pathways for the Green and Just Transition (2025–2030).

V. Conclusion: Return to a Resilient Transition Scenario

The stagnation of EU Member States' efforts under a baseline risk scenario is driven by a combination of factors: fiscal tightening, short-term challenges prompting budgetary reprioritisation, and political instability and fragmentation. Climate finance remains insufficient overall and lacks uniform and effective safeguards. **Although the EU is striving to integrate environmental objectives within its defence and competitiveness agendas, doubts persist regarding monitoring mechanisms and the risk of greenwashing.** Current developments indicate that despite its efforts, the EU remains off track to meet its 2030 and 2050 environmental targets. However, within the MFF 2028-2034 and the current presidency agenda, there is a clear intention to maintain climate concerns on the policy agenda. **Flexibility, competitiveness, and security priorities must not – and do not need to – undermine or compete with environmental funding.** Rather than mere coexistence, these objectives should be mutually reinforcing.

THE MFF PROPOSAL PRESENTS A DOUBLE-EDGED SWORD.

While establishing a general climate-related spending target could risk diluting green investments and allow further weaknesses in monitoring, the proposal also holds the potential to embed sustainability goals across sectors through cross-policy alignment.

At the national level, fragmentation across climate, industrial, and social policy domains has led to relevant initiatives operating in silos.

Climate goals may progress without adequate consideration of social equity, while industrial policies often lack robust decarbonisation benchmarks. This fragmentation diminishes the transformative potential of the transition and raises the risk of public disillusionment. **Although some policies demonstrate the ambition needed to meet climate challenges, they are frequently delayed or deprioritised as new short-term issues emerge.**

Given the varying political capacities and recurring instability across EU Member States, policy coordination and effective funding allocation remain challenging. In this context of national uncertainty and occasional shifts away from climate priorities, the European Union's climate leadership could face increasing strain.

Encouraging a more active and cohesive approach might help strengthen policy coherence and strategic integration across both EU and national levels. Integrating climate considerations alongside the short-term challenges Europe faces today—and those that may emerge in the future—could open a path toward a more resilient, equitable, and sustainable transition.

Developing a coordinated fiscal and green policy framework could also help ensure that the Green Deal retains its transformative potential, rather than becoming a largely symbolic agenda. Short-term challenges, despite concentrating political momentum, do not oppose or contradict climate protection. The shift toward competitiveness and security does not necessarily need to further weaken the position of climate change within the political agenda. Furthermore, the Green and Just Transition can take multiple routes, with each dimension reinforcing and complementing the other. The following table outlines some of the challenges and potential strategies to overcome them that Europe could pursue to foster a more favourable climate scenario.

Figure 14. Scenario Matrix: Potential Strategies to achieve a Resilient Transition Scenario.

Organizational profile

SLYCAN Trust is a non-profit think tank working on climate change, sustainable development, climate finance, risk management, entrepreneurship, biodiversity and ecosystem conservation, security, and social justice including gender and youth empowerment. Our work spans the national, regional, and global level from policy analysis and evidence-based research to capacity-building, technical support provision, and on-the-ground implementation.

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